

The Value of Controlled Vocabularies for Research Data

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We acknowledge the Traditional Owners and Custodians of the land and sea in all nations. We honour their profound connections to land, water, biodiversity and culture and pay our respects to their Elders past, present and emerging.

Goals of Research Data Repositories

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2. Make that data available for further use
3. Data are curated to the most complete level possible, and are *easy to find*

Choosing a Data Repository

Repository provides	Best	Adequate
DOI (persistence, immutability)	X	X
Revision control	X	X
API	X	
Measurement-level metadata	X	
Data validation (structural and/or scientific)	X	
Contributes to larger networks	X	
Other services, e.g., data exploration tools	X	

Findability, reusability

Metadata and data formatting requirements

DRYAD

UNICAMP

zenodo

figshare

Domain Specific Citation metadata

Domain Specific Science data

ORNL DAAC

GBIF

AMERIFLUX

PhenoCam

NCBI

SiBBR

Specialized format and metadata

SPIDER-MAN

SPIDER-MAN

SPIDER-MAN 2

SPIDER-MAN

SPIDER-MAN 3

SPIDER-MAN 2

SPIDER-MAN

SPIDER-MAN 3

SPIDER-MAN 2

SPIDER-MAN INTO THE SPIDER-VERSE

SPIDER-MAN

SPIDER-MAN 3

SPIDER-MAN 2

SPIDER-MAN
INTO THE SPIDER-VERSE

SPIDER-MAN

SPIDER-MAN 3

SPIDER-MAN 2

SPIDER-MAN INTO THE SPIDER-VERSE

*I know that
an LTER site
near Santa
Barbara has
data*

*I know that
an LTER site
near Santa
Barbara has
data*

*And so does
Google*

The image shows a Google search interface for the query "santa barbara lter". The search results page displays several filters: "Last updated", "Download format" (set to "All"), "Usage rights" (set to "Free"), and "Topic". Below the filters, there are buttons for "Table", "Document", "Image", "Text", "Archive", and "Other".

The search results section shows "100+ datasets found". The first result is highlighted with a grey background and a red circle containing the letter "E". The result is titled "Data from: SBC LTER: Land Ocean Reef: Foodweb Stable..." and includes the URL "portal.edirepository.org" and the update date "Updated May 22, 2014".

The second result is titled "SBC LTER: Land: Hydrology: Daily precipitation from Santa..." and includes the URL "portal.edirepository.org" and the update date "Updated May 22, 2014".

The third result is titled "Data from: Santa Barbara Coastal site, station Santa..." and includes the URL "portal.edirepository.org" and the update date "Updated Oct 29, 2014".

The fourth result is partially visible, titled "Data from: SBC LTER:".

The right-hand side of the page shows a detailed view of the first result, titled "Data from: SBC LTER: Land Ocean Reef: Foodweb Stable Isotopes: Isotope data". It includes a "Related Article" link, a blue button labeled "Explore at Environmental Data Initiative", a "Unique identifier" with a DOI link, a "Dataset updated" date of May 22, 2014, and "Dataset provided by" Environmental Data Initiative. Below this is an "Area covered" section with a map showing the location of the study area near Santa Barbara, California, including labels for "National Forest", "Solvang", "Gaviota", and "Santa Barbara".

schema.org

... standardized vocabulary ... to mark up website content with metadata about itself – *wikipedia*

Such markup can be recognized by search engines

<https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/>

Dataset Search

amazon rainforest

- ☰ Deforested area in the **Amazon rainforest** in Brazil 2004-2020
- ☰ **Amazon rainforest** population in Brazil 1970-2020
- ☰ Change in deforested area in the **Amazon rainforest** in Brazil 2000-2021
- ☰ Opinions on the importance of the **Amazon rainforest** 2020

Vocabulary Features

Vocabularies:

- Fall on a spectrum
- More complex structures yield more inferential power

OWL Ontologies:

- Describe classes, instances, properties, and relationships
- Provide consistent machine-readable interpretations

Structure

LTBR Controlled Vocabulary

Home My account

processes

Home / processes

Term Metadata

processes

More specific terms

- NT1 physiological processes ▶
- NT1 resource management ▶
- NT1 biogeochemical processes ▶
- NT1 biological processes ▶
- NT1 community respiration
- NT1 disturbance ▶
- NT1 physical processes ▶
- NT1 scientific activities ▶
- NT1 accumulation ▶
- NT1 fertilization
- NT1 harvesting ▶
- NT1 landscape change ▶
- NT1 recovery
- NT1 restoration

What is Ontology?

Mechanism to represent knowledge for both humans and machines

RDF - A model for representing concepts and relationship between them

Graph - A collection of RDF data. Graphs are merged to create new representations of knowledge.

Linked Data

Image credit: <https://aws.amazon.com/neptune/knowledge-graphs-on-aws/>

Linked Data


```
<rdf:RDF
  xmlns:rdf="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#"
  xmlns:owl="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#">

  <rdf:Description rdf:about="https://orcid.org/ 0000-0003-2926-8353">
    <owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-
ns#type">
      <owl:Class rdf:about="https://schema.org/Person" />
    </owl:ObjectProperty>
    <owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="https://schema.org/memberOf">
      <owl:Class rdf:about="https://ror.org/00var5q80" />
    </owl:ObjectProperty>
  </rdf>

</rdf:RDF>
```

The Environment Ontology

environmentontology.org

The screenshot shows the homepage of the Environment Ontology website. On the left is a navigation menu with links: "The Environment Ontology", "About EnvO", "Annotation guidelines", "Browse EnvO", "Downloads", "Participate", and "Contact". The main content area features a large image of a snowy owl with the text "Browse EnvO" overlaid. Below the image, there is introductory text about the ontology's size and how to use it, including instructions on creating subsets and finding terms. A section titled "A number of portals and ontology browsing interfaces harvest ENVO" lists the "European Bioinformatics Institute's Ontology Lookup Service" and provides a bulleted list of tips for using the search box, such as pausing after keywords and using interactive signs in the hierarchy viewer. A note explains how to navigate to relevant sub-hierarchy terms. At the bottom, there is a link to the "Downloads" page.

EnvO

The Environment Ontology

About EnvO

Annotation guidelines

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Browse EnvO

ENVO is a fairly big ontology with hundreds of its own terms and many more imported terms. All that content is what helps machines reason over the ontology, but it can make browsing it - in its entirety - a bit daunting.

If you plan on using ENVO regularly, your or your data managers or curators can make a [subset](#) of the terms, tailored to your community's needs. As long as those terms are linked to the ENVO IRIs (see our [Annotation guidelines](#) for more on that), all should be well. Please [contact us](#) if you'd like some support.

If you'd prefer that we host and maintain a subset for your community, please post an issue on our [GitHub tracker](#) and requesting an [ENVO subset](#) for your project or community. We can export subsets in a variety of formats, to make life easier.

If you or your team(s) can't find a term they need in subset, please search the full ontology through services like the OLS, noted below. If it's still not there, please request a new term (more on that [here](#)).

A number of portals and ontology browsing interfaces harvest ENVO. One of these is the [European Bioinformatics Institute's Ontology Lookup Service](#). Once you're there, you can navigate ENVO by:

- **Typing a term** into the search box.
 - Please pause a moment after you've entered your keyword(s) and all the terms with matches will be suggested. Hitting return immediately after entering your keyword(s) will take you to the first entry with a match.
- **Browsing interactively** by clicking on the "*" signs in the hierarchy viewer below the search.
 - **Note:** You'll see some "upper-level" terms like "continuant" in the tree which you probably don't need. To get to the sub-hierarchy that's relevant to you, use the search box to get to something more general or related like "biome", "environmental material", or "environmental system process". From there, you should be closer to your desired term.

If you'd prefer to download and work with a release version of ENVO yourself, please visit our [Downloads](#) page.

The Environment Ontology

ENVO's representation of an oasis (From Buttigieg et al. 2016)

The Environment Ontology

ENVO's representation of a volcanic eruption process (From Buttigieg et al. 2016)

Constructing a Vocabulary

Romain David et al
2021. *Data dictionary cookbook for research data interoperability at global scale. Research Data Alliance Plenary 17 (RDA P17), Edinburgh, remotely. Zenodo.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4683066>

Data dictionary cookbook

Generic	Parsec	Kakila	Erinha Advance
Define your community perimeter [Scientific Questions]	<i>Community perimeter defined by:</i> [Scientific Questions] Can some satellite images be used as proxies for socio-economic indicators?	<i>Community perimeter defined by:</i> [Scientific Questions] Can we characterize cetacean presence in the waters of the Guadeloupe archipelago using several citizen science databases?	<i>Community perimeter defined by:</i> [Scientific Questions] Can Biosafety level 4 laboratories compare their virologic in vivo studies results?
Explain and convince [Data dictionary principles]	[Data dictionary principles] <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Choose common definitions to enable comparisons between countries- Validate reusable definitions to ensure reproducibility of project results	[Data dictionary principles] <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Choose common vocabulary to describe fields from heterogeneous databases- Adopt common variables description and values between databases	[Data dictionary principles] <ul style="list-style-type: none">- List all in vivo models, viruses, protocols and their data sensitivity- List and homogenize variables description for possible meta-analyses
Identify your scientific objects [List of ENTITIES]	<i>About the scientific question, examples of</i> [ENTITIES] <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Municipality- Satellite images- Sectors- ...	<i>About the scientific question, examples of</i> [ENTITIES] <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Cetacean observation- Observers- ...	<i>About the scientific question, examples of</i> [ENTITIES] <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Virus- Hamster- ...
Identify the <u>aspects</u> of your scientific objects you need to assess [List of QUALITY] for each Entity	<i>For each entities, examples of</i> [QUALITIES] <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Human Development Indicators of [Municipality or Satellite images or Sectors]- Population of [Municipality or Satellite images or Sectors]- ...	<i>For each entities, examples of</i> [QUALITIES] <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Individual Species (Cetacean observation)- Individual Length (Cetacean observation)- Experience (of Observer)- ...	<i>For each entities, examples of</i> [QUALITIES] <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Mortality rate (of the virus)- Age (of the hamster)- Breed (of the hamster)- ...
Name and define necessary variables and their dimensions: [Variables names: Entity_Quality_Dimensions] for each Quality of each Entity	<i>Due for each qualities, examples of</i> [Variables names: Entity_Quality_Dimensions] <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Municipality_HDV_value- Municipality_population_value- ...	<i>For each qualities, examples of</i> [Variables names: Entity_Quality_Dimensions(&unit)] <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Cetacean_Obs_Length- Observer_Exp_category- ...	<i>For each qualities, examples of</i> [Variables names: Entity_Quality_Dimensions] <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Virus_Mortality_Percentage- Hamster_Age_Nbweeks- Hamster_Breed_BreedName- ...
<u>Reuse existing standards, vocabularies, concepts and definitions</u>	Reuse existing vocabularies and ontologies, with a challenge: when there are several, choosing the better terms. <i>All terms are community approved</i>	The two challenges are: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- to obtain a consensus for variables values between databases- to align with the existing data to Darwin Core vocabulary <i>All terms are community approved</i>	The two challenge are: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- to Reuse existing vocabularies and ontologies (if several, choosing the better one).- to obtain a consensus between variables names and definitions. <i>All terms must be community approved</i>
Validate by the whole community [List of DEFINITIONS]	Data dictionary with [List of DEFINITIONS] approved by the whole community contain ALL [Scientific Questions], [List of ENTITIES], [List of QUALITIES], [Variables names: Entity_Quality_Dimensions_Units] and variables definitions		

Repository Role

Semantic Search

The screenshot shows the DataONE search interface. The search results for 'carbon' are displayed, including a list of datasets and a map view. The search results include:

- Dataset 1:** Jennifer E. Caselle, Peter M. Carlson, Chris Honeyman, Avrey Parsons-Field, and Katie D. Koehn. 2020. **PISCO UCSB Subtidal Invertebrate Recruitment Data.** PISCO MN. doi:10.6085/AA/PISCO_UCSB_Subtidal_Invertebrate_Recruitment.1.1.
- Dataset 2:** Jennifer E. Caselle, Peter M. Carlson, Chris Honeyman, Avrey Parsons-Field, and Katie D. Koehn. 2020. **PISCO UCSB Subtidal Fish Recruitment Data.** PISCO MN. doi:10.6085/AA/PISCO_UCSB_Fish_Recruitment.1.2.

The map view shows a grid of data points over a geographic area, with a legend indicating 'Satellite' and 'Terrain' views. The map data includes values such as 6481, 297, 222, 30, 25, 26, 19, 27, 246, 205, 2772, 484, 16, 120, 83, 28, 9, 33, 103, 393, 1369, 1163, 287, 150, 61, 208, 6, 75, 71, 653, 370, 352, 781, 332, 313, 175, 61, 306, 223, 689, 489, 4666, 1998, 1457, 5927, 2501, 317, 299, 967, 97, 12104, 5243, 8985, 1658, 4947, 17097, 1372, 640, 88, 141, 770, 43238, 13229, 5931, 6579, 12921, 876, 435, 94, 247, 294, 6833, 18920, 2086, 12049, 3393, 1612, 322, 232, 229, 49, 203, 1286, 1011, 9134, 2058, 385, 740, 1097, 107, 51, 66, 384, 487, 893, 926, 2521, 221, 73, 592, 125, 192, 235, 1190, 636, 715, 1467, 514, 250, 1010, 226, 101, 641, 407, 2202, 231, 419, 101, 349, 789, 576, 1277, 318, 125, 769, 1323, 155, 96, 22, 1.6K, Terms of Use.

Data tagged with URIs enable semantic search, and eventually LOD.

<https://edirepository.org/>

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Repository provides	Best	Adequate
DOI (persistence, immutability)	X	X
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Measurement-level metadata	X	
Data validation (structural and/or scientific)	X	
Contributes to larger networks	X	
Other services*	X*	

Inter-University Research Institute Corporation
National Institutes for the Humanities
**Research Institute for
Humanity and Nature**

**TOKYO
METROPOLITAN
UNIVERSITY**

USP

Thank you

RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

The Nature Conservancy

**THE UNIVERSITY
OF QUEENSLAND
AUSTRALIA**